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Key Words: Reliability model generation, Markov models, Reliability analysis.

Abstract

Markov models can be used to analyze the reliability of virtually any fault-tolerant system. However, the process of delineating all of the states and transitions in the model of a complex system can be devastatingly tedious and error-prone. The Abstract Semi-Markov Specification Interface to the SURE Tool (ASSIST) program allows the user to describe the Markov model in a high-level language. Instead of listing the individual states of the model, the user specifies the rules governing the behavior of the system, and these are used to automatically generate the model. A small number of statements in the abstract language can describe a very large, complex model. Because no assumptions are made about the system being modeled, ASSIST can be used to generate models describing the behavior of any type of system. The ASSIST program and its input language are described and illustrated by examples.

Introduction

New advances in computation, such as the Semi-Markov Range Evaluator (SURE) program, enable the accurate solution of extremely large and complex Markov models (Refs. 1 and 2). (In this paper, the term Markov will be used to refer to both Markov and the more general semi-Markov models.) However, the generation by hand of the large models needed to capture the complex failure and reconfiguration behavior of most realistic fault-tolerant architectures has been an intractable problem. Much research has been done on techniques for model pruning and state aggregation to simplify the models, at the expense of accuracy (Refs. 3 and 4).

Many of the early fault-tolerant architectures, such as the Software Implemented Fault Tolerance (SIFT) system, are relatively simple to model. Even the early complex systems were usually made up of subsystems that can be modeled independently. However, as flight-critical systems become more complex and more highly integrated, the Markov models to describe them will become enormously complex. The complexity of the model stems from the interactions between failure and recovery processes of the various subsystems, which can no longer be modeled independently.

Often even the most complex characteristics of a system can be described by relatively simple rules. The models only become complex because these few rules combine many times to form models with large numbers of states and transitions between them. The rules describing the behavior of each subsystem can be developed and verified separately, then the submodels are easily combined to accurately model the behavior of the entire integrated system. An abstract, high-level language for describing system behavior rules and a methodology for automatically generating Markov models from the language were developed by Ricky Butler (ref. 5). The ASSIST computer program (Ref. 6) allows the user to specify the behavior rules of the model in this abstract language, then the Markov model is generated automatically from the rules. The ASSIST program was written in Pascal and executes on a VAX 11/750. The Markov model is output in the format required for input to the SURE program. For Markov analysis programs

requiring a different form of input for the Markov model, a simple program could be written to modify the model description file.

The abstract model definition and the automatic model generation strategy are described. Analysis of an example fault-tolerant architecture, a triad of processors with cold spare processors, shows how the behavior of a system can be captured by a few general rules. The syntax of the ASSIST input language is then described and demonstrated by creating a model to describe the fault behavior of the example architecture. The flexibility of the abstract language is demonstrated by expanding the example to model multiple triads of processors sharing a pool of cold spare processors.

Model Definition

A Markov model consists of a number of system states and transitions between them. Each state is defined by a state vector, where each element of the vector takes on an integer value within a defined range. An element can represent any meaningful characteristic, such as the number of good components of one type in the system, or the number of faulty components of another type in use. Each element is assigned an appropriate variable name for ease of reference. The state space variables for the model and their valid ranges are defined in the "space" statement. The user specifies the initial system state in the "start" statement. This establishes the initial values of the state space variables for the generation of the model.

The transitions represent the elapsed time between system states which are stochastic processes defined by probability distributions. In the restricted class of Markov models, all transitions are exponentially distributed and are completely defined by a simple rate parameter. In the more general semi-Markov model, any distribution can be used to describe the elapsed time. Transitions between states in the model are specified using transition statements. These statements have three main parts: a condition expression, a destination expression, and a rate expression. The first expression is a boolean expression to describe the state space variable values of states for which the transition is valid. The second expression defines the destination state for the transition in terms of state space variable values. The third expression defines the distribution of elapsed time for the transition.

Absorbing states of the model (i.e., states with no transitions leaving them) represent system failure. Typically, the reliability engineer must calculate the probability of entering an absorbing state within the specified mission time. The absorbing state or "death" conditions of the model must be defined in terms of state space values. These "death" conditions could be system failure or the onset of degraded performance operation or other situations resulting from failures.

The ASSIST program reads an input file containing the model definition rules and creates two output files: the model file and an optional listing file. The model file describes all of the transitions between states in the Markov model and their corresponding rates in the format required for input to the SURE program. The states are specified by integers. To make the model

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easier to understand, this file is annotated with the state space variables of each state in comments, which SURE will ignore. For example:

1(* 6,0,0 *), 2(* 5,1,0 *) = 3*LAMBDA;

denotes a transition between state 1 and state 2 at exponential rate 3λ , where state 1 is defined in ASSIST as (6,0,0) and state 2 is (5,1,0):

In addition to a listing of the ASSIST input file, the optional listing file contains a list of the destination state of each arc leaving each non-death state in the model. Destination states that are death states are annotated with an asterisk. The listing file also contains a list of the mappings between the SURE state numbers and the state space variables of that state in ASSIST. The optional listing file is useful for verifying that the model generated accurately describes the intended system behavior.

Constants and variables based on state space variables can be defined in the input language and used in subsequent statements. Statements in the ASSIST input file that are put inside quotes are copied into the model output file and are not otherwise processed by ASSIST. These statements are put in the front of the SURE input file with the constant definition statements. Comments may also be included in the input file.

ASSIST Model Generation

The ASSIST program builds the model from the initial "start" state by recursively applying the transition rules. Before application of a rule, ASSIST checks all of the "death" conditions to see if the current state is a "death" state. Since a "death" state denotes system failure, no transitions can leave a "death" state. All of the transition rules are then evaluated, and transitions to new states are generated where appropriate. When all possible branches terminate in a "death" state, model building is complete. The output file contains a definition of each transition and its rate. A listing file is also generated to assist the user in determining whether the model generated describes the intended system behavior.

The specific algorithm used to generate the model is as follows. Initially, the READY SET contains only the "start" state of the model. Each state in the READY SET is processed in the following manner. If the state meets any of the "death" conditions, then that state is a "death" state, and no transitions can leave it, so the state is removed from the READY SET. If the state is not a "death" state, then each transition rule is applied to the state in the following manner to generate all possible transitions leaving the state. If the

condition expression of the transition rule evaluates to true for the current state, then the destination expression in the rule is used to determine the destination state. If this state is within the bounds of the state space parameters, then this is a valid transition. If the destination state has not already been defined in the model, then a unique integer is assigned to the new state, and it is added to the READY SET. If the destination state was already defined in the model, then it was placed in the READY SET for processing when it was first defined. The rate of the transition is determined from the rate expression, and the transition description is printed to the SURE model file. After all of the transition rules have been applied to the state, it is removed from the READY SET.

Example Architecture

The example architecture consists of a triad of processors each executing the same program plus a pool of two cold spare processors. The three processors receive identical inputs so all non-faulty processors produce the same output, and the three outputs are voted. Any incorrect outputs are masked by the voting as long as a majority of the active processors are non-faulty. A faulty processor is detected by the voter and is replaced with a cold spare processor if one is available. For simplicity, this process is assumed to be exponential for this example. There is no fault detection for spare processors until they become active. The Markov model to describe this system is shown in figure 1.

The states in the example model are described by the vector (NP, NFP, NS, NFS), where

NP = Number of active processors,
 NFP = Number of failed active processors,
 NS = Number of cold spare processors, and
 NFS = Number of failed cold spare processors.

The fault and recovery behavior of the example system is described by the following rules:

1. The failure rate of each active processor is λ .
2. The failure rate of cold spare processors is γ .
3. A failed active processor is replaced by a spare processor at rate δ .
4. System failure occurs unless a majority of the active processors are non-faulty.

Rules 1 through 3 above describe the transitions between states in the model. The fourth rule describes the "death" states of the model. The system starts with three non-faulty, active processors and two non-faulty, cold spare processors, thus the start state is (3, 0, 2, 0).

Figure 1. Markov model for a triad with two cold spares.

Creating an Example Input File

The basic statements used in ASSIST are:

SPACE statement
START statement
DEATHIF statement
TRANTO statements
FOR statements
PRUNEIF statements

The ASSIST input file must contain one SPACE statement and one START statement. The file may contain multiple DEATHIF and TRANTO statements, and these statements may be placed inside of FOR loops. Multiple PRUNEIF statements may also be included to reduce the number of states in the model. The use of the basic statements to describe the fault behavior of the example architecture will be demonstrated in this section.

SPACE Statement

The SPACE statement specifies the state space on which the Markov model is defined. The state space is defined by a n-dimensional vector where each component of the vector defines an attribute of the system being modeled. In the example architecture described above the state space is (NP, NFP, NS, NFS). This would be defined in ASSIST by the statement

```
SPACE = (NP: 0..3, NFP: 0..3, NS: 0..2, NFS: 0..2);
```

A state space variable can also be a one-dimensional array. Arrays are useful, for example, in modeling systems in which the specific processor that has failed must be modeled instead of simply the number of failed processors. The TRANTO and DEATHIF statements affecting components modeled with arrays are often placed within FOR loops. The section entitled "Modifying the Example" shows an example of how arrays may be used.

START Statement

The START statement indicates which state represents the initial state of the system being modeled, i.e. the probability the system is in this state at time 0 is 1. In the example architecture the initial state is (3, 0, 2, 0). This is specified as follows:

```
START = (3, 0, 2, 0);
```

DEATHIF Statement

The DEATHIF statement specifies which states are absorbing or "death" states in the model. In the example problem, system failure occurs when half or more of the active processors are faulty. Thus, in all states of the Markov model where 2 times the value of NFP is greater than or equal to NP, system failure occurs. This is described with the following statement:

```
DEATHIF 2 * NFP >= NP;
```

TRANTO Statement

The TRANTO statement is used to describe the state transitions in the model. The model is generated by applying the TRANTO rules to each state in the model in a recursive manner. Each TRANTO expression consists of three basic parts: the condition expression, the destination expression, and the rate expression. The condition expression is a boolean expression that determines which states of the model this rule will be applied to. The destination expression defines the destination state of each transition by specifying the change in one or more of the state space variables from the source to destination state. The destination state can be specified using positional or assigned values. The rate expression defines the distribution of elapsed time for the transition to be added to the model. This

expression may contain FOR loop variables and state space variables.

There are three ways of expressing the distribution of elapsed time between states in the SURE program that are supported in ASSIST. Slow exponential transitions are specified by the transition rate. Fast transitions may be specified by two different methods: White's method or the fast exponential method. The syntax for White's method consists of three real expressions:

```
<"mu", "sig", "frac">
```

where

"mu" = the conditional mean transition time,
"sig" = the conditional standard deviation of the transition time, and
"frac" = the transition probability.

The third parameter is optional. If it is omitted, the transition probability is assumed to be 1.0.

The syntax of the fast exponential rate expression is:

```
FAST "rate"
```

where "rate" is a real constant expression. The SURE program automatically calculates the conditional moments from the unconditional rates given in this expression. In the simple case with only one transition leaving a state, the following two expressions are equivalent:

```
<1/alpha, 1/alpha, 1>  
FAST alpha.
```

For more information on specifying transition rates, see Reference 2.

In the example problem, the failure rate of each active processor is λ . This type of transition is possible from every state in which there are unfailed active processors. This condition can be described by $NP > NFP$. The destination state for this type of transition is identical to the current state, except that the number of faulty processors is greater by one. This can be described by the destination expression $NFP = NFP + 1$. ASSIST assumes that the other state space variables do not change. Since each of the unfailed active processors can fail, the rate of this transition is $(NP - NFP)$ times λ . This is described by the rate expression $(NP - NFP)*LAMBDA$ where LAMBDA is a constant defined to be equal to λ . The entire statement is thus:

```
IF NP > NFP TRANTO NFP = NFP+1 BY (NP-NFP)*LAMBDA;
```

By similar reasoning, the state transitions due to failures of cold spare processors can be defined by:

```
IF NS > NFS TRANTO NFS = NFS+1 BY (NS-NFS)*GAMMA;
```

where GAMMA is a constant defined to be equal to γ .

The third type of transitions are those due to reconfiguration. A failed active processor is replaced by a spare processor at rate δ . This transition is possible from any state in which there exist one or more failed active processors and one or more spares, defined by the condition expression $NFP > 0$ AND $NS > 0$.

The cold spare processor selected may have failed before reconfiguration. If one or more of the spare processors has failed, then the failed processor will be replaced with a failed spare processor with probability (NFS/NS) . If all of the spare processors have failed then $(NFS/NS)=1$, and the probability of selecting a failed spare is 1. The failed processor will be replaced with a working processor with probability $(1 - (NFS/NS))$. If none of the spare processors have failed,

then the probability of using a working spare is 1, and since $NFS=0$, then $(1-(NFS/NS))=1$.

Replacement of the failed processor with a failed spare processor is only possible if there exist one or more failed spare processors, $NFS > 0$. The destination state will have the number of failed processors stay the same. The number of spare processors will decrease by one, and the number of failed spares will decrease by one. The destination expression can thus be defined by $NS = NS-1$, $NFS = NFS-1$. Since we are assuming the recovery process is exponentially distributed, the FAST rate technique can be used. The basic rate of replacing a known faulty processor must be multiplied by the probability that the failed spare was used (NFS/NS) to include the possibility of replacing a faulty processor with a faulty spare. The resulting expression is thus:

```
IF NFP > 0 AND NS > 0 THEN
  IF NFS > 0 TRANTO NS = NS-1, NFS = NFS-1
    BY FAST (NFS/NS)*DELTA;
ENDIF;
```

where DELTA is a constant set equal to δ .

Replacement of the failed processor with a working spare is only possible when there exists one or more nonfailed spare processors, $NS > NFS$. In this case, the destination state has the number of failed processors decreased by one and the number of spare processors decreased by one. The resulting expression is thus:

```
IF NFP > 0 AND NS > 0 THEN
  IF NS > NFS TRANTO NFP = NFP-1, NS = NS-1
    BY FAST (NFS/NS)*DELTA;
ENDIF;
```

As may be seen from the last two examples, multiple condition expressions of TRANTO statements can be nested. An ELSE statement can also be used.

FOR Statements

Many times several TRANTO or DEATHIF statements are needed which are identical except they operate on different state space variables. The different state space variables can be put in an array, and the FOR statement can be used to define several TRANTO or DEATHIF rules at once. Consider a system in which system failure occurs when half or more of any of three types of components are faulty. An array NA of range 1 to 3 could represent the number of each type of component active in the system, and an array NF of range 1 to 3 could represent the number of each type of component that is faulty and active. The "death" condition could be described by the following:

```
FOR I = 1,3;
  DEATHIF 2 * NF[I] >= NA[I];
ENDFOR;
```

Thus, in all states of the Markov model where 2 times the value of NF for one of the three components is greater than or equal to NA for the same component, system failure occurs.

PRUNEIF Statements

The PRUNEIF statement can be used to automatically truncate the Markov model. Assume the probability of more than M component failures occurring during a mission is negligible compared to the probability of system failure. Using NFC as a state space variable to represent the number of failed components, the following statement appropriately truncates the model:

```
PRUNEIF NFC > M;
```

The model is truncated by assuming system failure when the truncation criteria is met, so this method is con-

servative. All of the pruned states are aggregated together as one state, which is state number 1. Thus, the contribution to system failure due to pruning can easily be determined from examining the SURE output.

The ASSIST Input File

The example architecture may thus be described using ASSIST as follows:

```
N_PROCS = 3;      (* Number of active processors *)
N_SPARES = 2;     (* Number of cold spare processor *)
LAMBDA = 1E-4;    (* Failure rate of active processor *)
GAMMA = 1E-5;     (* Failure rate of spare processor *)
DELTA = 3.6E3;    (* Reconfiguration rate *)
```

```
SPACE = (NP: 0..N_PROCS, (* Number active procs *)
         NFP:0..N_PROCS, (* Failed active procs *)
         NS: 0..N_SPARES, (* Number spare procs *)
         NFS:0..N_SPARES); (* Failed spare procs *)
START = (N_PROCS, 0, N_SPARES, 0);
```

```
DEATHIF 2 * NFP >= NP;
IF NP > NFP TRANTO NFP = NFP+1 BY (NP-NFP)*LAMBDA;
  (* Active processor failure *)
IF NS > NFS TRANTO NFS = NFS+1 BY NS*GAMMA;
  (* Spare processor failure *)
IF (NFP > 0 AND NS > 0) THEN
  IF NS > NFS TRANTO (NP, NFP-1, NS-1, NFS)
    BY FAST (1-(NFS/NS))*DELTA;
  (* Replace failed processor with working spare *)
  IF NFS > 0 TRANTO (NP, NFP, NS-1, NFS-1)
    BY FAST (NFS/NS)*DELTA;
  (* Replace failed processor with failed spare *)
ENDIF;
```

By changing the value of N_SPARES, a similar system with a different number of initial spares may be modeled.

An Example Using Arrays

The example above can be expanded to model a system with several triads and a pool of spares using array state space variables. If two or more processors in an active triad fail then the system fails. As long as spares are available, a faulty processor in a triad is replaced from the spares pool. If no spares are available, then the triad is broken up and the nonfaulty processors are added to the pool of spares.

This example is very similar to the first example, except that the DEATHIF statement and TRANTO statements pertaining to triads must be put inside FOR loops to handle all of the triads. The only significant changes to the model are a new transition type and a new type of system failure. The new transition is the breakup of a triad when it fails and there are no spares. System failure by exhaustion must also be modeled, which requires an extra state space variable and a new DEATHIF statement.

```
INPUT N_TRIADS; (* Number of triads initially *)
INPUT N_SPARES; (* Number of cold spare processors *)
N_PROCS = 3;    (* Number of active processors *)
LAMBDA = 1E-4;  (* Failure rate of active processors *)
GAMMA = 1E-5;   (* Failure rate of spare processors *)
DELTA1 = 3.6E3; (* Reconfig. rate to switch in spare *)
DELTA2 = 5.1E3; (* Reconfig. rate to break up triad *)
```

```
SPACE = (NP: ARRAY[1..N_TRIADS] OF 0..N_PROCS,
         (* Number of active processors per triad *)
         NFP: ARRAY[1..N_TRIADS] OF 0..N_PROCS,
         (* Failed active processors per triad *)
         NS, (* Number of spare processors *)
         NFS, (* Number of failed spare processors *)
         NT: 0..N_TRIADS); (* Non-failed triads *)
START = (N_TRIADS OF N_PROCS, N_TRIADS OF 0, N_SPARES,
         0, N_TRIADS);
```

```

IF NS > NFS TRANTO NFS = NFS+1 BY NS*GAMMA;
(* Spare processor failure *)
FOR J=1,N TRIADS
IF NP[J] > NFP[J] TRANTO NFP[J] = NFP[J]+1
BY (NP[J]-NFP[J])*LAMBDA;
(* Active processor failure *)
IF NFP[J] > 0 THEN
IF NS > 0 THEN
IF NS > NFS TRANTO NFP[J] = NFP[J]-1, NS = NS-1
BY FAST (1-(NFS/NS))*DELTA1;
(* Replace processor with working spare *)
IF NFS > 0 TRANTO NS = NS-1, NFS = NFS-1
BY FAST (NFS/NS)*DELTA1;
(* Replace processor with failed spare *)
ELSE
TRANTO NP[J] = 0, NFP[J] = 0, NT = NT-1,
NS = NP[J]-NFP[J] BY FAST DELTA2;
(* Break up failed triad *)
(* if no spares available *)
ENDIF;
ENDIF;
DEATHIF 2 * NFP[J] >= NP[J] AND NP[J] > 0;
(* Two faults in active triad is system failure *)
ENDFOR;
DEATHIF NT = 0; (* System failure by exhaustion *)

```

Since variable-sized arrays were used, a system with any number of initial triads may be modeled by setting the constant N_TRIADS. The number of spares initially is set with the constant N_SPARES. Table 1 shows that changing these two constants has a dramatic effect on the number of states in the model generated.

		Number of Spares			
		0	1	2	3
Number	1	4	10	19	31
of	2	45	61	85	117
Triads	3	219	259	319	399
	4	889	985	1129	1321

Table 1. Number of states in model for various initial configurations of example 2.

An Example Using Pruning

The example used in this section was taken from Reference 7, where it was used to demonstrate the ability of the Hybrid Automated Reliability Predictor (HARP) program to solve very large models. The example system contains twenty components of seven different types. The failure conditions of the system are defined by the fault tree given in figure 2. Without considering coverage failures, this fault tree converts to a Markov chain containing 24,533 states and over 335,391 transitions according to Reference 7. The ASSIST input file to define this model is given below. A PRUNEIF statement is included to prune the model at the third component failure level.

```

L_PS = 3.0E-5; (* Failure rate of power supplies *)
L_IC = 1.5E-5; (* Failure rate of input controllers *)
L_DC = 7.0E-6; (* Failure rate of data collectors *)
L_CPU = 3.26E-5; (* Failure rate of CPUs *)
L_BUS = 1.0E-5; (* Failure rate of 1553 busses *)
L_OD = 3.0E-6; (* Failure rate of output drivers *)
L_CR = 4.26E-6; (* Failure rate of CCDL receivers *)

SPACE = (PSF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed power supplies *)
ICF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed input controllers *)
DCF:ARRAY[1..2], (* Failed data collectors *)
CPUF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed CPUs *)
BUSF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed 1553 buses *)
ODF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed output drivers *)
CRF:ARRAY[1..3], (* Failed CCDL receivers *)
NFC); (* Total number of component failures *)
START = (21 OF 0);

PRUNEIF (NFC >= 3); (* Prunes model at 4th *)
(* component failure level *)
ONEDEATH = 1; (* This statement causes all the death *)
(* states to be aggregated into one state *)

(* The DEATHIF statements can be determined *)
(* directly from the fault tree description *)
DEATHIF (PSF[1]+ICF[1]+DCF[1]>0) AND
(PSF[2]+ICF[2]+DCF[2]>0);
DEATHIF (PSF[1]+ICF[1]+CPUF[1]+BUSF[1]>0) AND
(PSF[2]+ICF[2]+CPUF[2]+BUSF[2]>0) AND
(PSF[3]+ICF[3]+CPUF[3]+BUSF[3]>0);
DEATHIF (PSF[1]+ICF[1]+CPUF[1]+ODF[1]+CRF[1]>0) AND
(PSF[2]+ICF[2]+CPUF[2]+ODF[2]+CRF[2]>0) AND
(PSF[3]+ICF[3]+CPUF[3]+ODF[3]+CRF[3]>0);

(* Failures of each type of component: *)
FOR I = 1,3;
IF PSF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, PSF[I]=1 BY L_PS;
IF ICF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, ICF[I]=1 BY L_IC;
IF CPUF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, CPUF[I]=1 BY L_CPU;
IF BUSF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, BUSF[I]=1 BY L_BUS;
IF ODF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, ODF[I]=1 BY L_OD;
IF CRF[I] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, CRF[I]=1 BY L_CR;
ENDFOR;
FOR J = 1,2;
IF DCF[J] = 0 TRANTO NFC=NFC+1, DCF[J]=1 BY L_DC;
ENDFOR;

```

The ASSIST file above generates a Markov model with only 203 states and 3658 transitions. The ASSIST program required approximately 300 CPU seconds to generate this model, and the SURE program required approximately 20 CPU seconds to solve the model for each of the 10 mission times. As shown in the following table, the conservative error due to pruning is at most 0.8% for each mission time. This pruned model is only approximately 1/100th the size of the full model of the system, yet the error is negligible.

Figure 2. Fault tree for example with pruning.

Mission (hours)	Unreliability		Error Due to	HARP
	Bounds		Pruning	Answers
1	2.704E-9	2.707E-9	2.222E-12	2.705E-9
2	1.082E-8	1.084E-8	1.777E-11	1.082E-8
3	2.435E-8	2.442E-8	6.000E-11	2.435E-8
4	4.329E-8	4.347E-8	1.422E-10	4.330E-8
5	6.766E-8	6.800E-8	2.777E-10	6.766E-8
6	9.745E-8	9.804E-8	4.799E-10	9.745E-8
7	1.327E-7	1.336E-7	7.620E-10	1.327E-7
8	1.733E-7	1.747E-7	1.138E-9	1.733E-7
9	2.194E-7	2.214E-7	1.620E-9	2.194E-7
10	2.709E-7	2.736E-7	2.222E-9	2.709E-7

This example dramatically shows the power of the PRUNEIF statement. Although the SURE program and many other Markov solvers could prune the model before analyzing it, pruning in ASSIST means the entire model never has to be generated.

Modeling Techniques

Modeling of systems using Markov models is still rather much of an art, even using the ASSIST program. As with any language, as the user becomes proficient he can more easily generate elegant, efficient models. States can often be aggregated by using fewer state space variables to describe the system states, thus creating a smaller model that can be analyzed more quickly by the Markov analysis tool. However, this often leads to rather complex TRANTO and DEATHIF statements, making the input file much more difficult to understand and verify.

Concluding Remarks

The use of the ASSIST program has been described and illustrated by several examples. This program allows the user to define a set of rules in an abstract language which are then used to automatically generate a Markov model. These rules correspond to the basic concepts used to create models of fault-tolerant systems. A small number of statements in the language can be used to describe a very large model. A variation in the system (such as in the number of initial spares) can be accomplished by changing only one line in the model definition, although such a change could represent a large increase in the size of the generated model. Model pruning techniques can be used to dramatically reduce the size of the generated model without significantly reducing accuracy, and the maximum error due to model pruning can easily be determined.

Although ASSIST has not been officially released, reliability engineers at Sperry Corporation, Boeing Military and Boeing Commercial Airplane Companies, the Charles Stark Draper Laboratory, and six other companies are using ASSIST to build models to input to the SURE reliability analysis program. The Integrated Airframe/Propulsion Control System Architecture (IAPSA II) study being performed by the Boeing Military Airplane Company used ASSIST to generate a complex

reliability model of sensors, actuators, and multi-channel fault-tolerant processors used in engine and flight control of an advanced high-performance aircraft design. ASSIST was used to model each subsystem, then the models were easily combined by ASSIST to produce a reliability model for the complex, integrated system.

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